

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS TO BE AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Test implementation of user-centered quality evaluation on selected services

MILESTONE 10

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS TO BE AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Milestone identifier	MS10
Milestone title	Test implementation of user-centered quality evaluation on selected services
Grant Agreement number	: 101079608
Project acronym	: OPERAS-PLUS
Project title	: On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS to be an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure
Funding Scheme	: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02
Project's coordinator Organisation	: Max Weber Stiftung – MWS
E-mail address	: kaiser@maxweberstiftung.de
Website	: https://www.operas-eu.org/projects/operas-plus/
WP and tasks contributing	: WP5
WP leader	: Franjo Pehar/UNIZD
Dissemination level	: Public (PU)
Due date	: 2025/04/30
Delivery date	: 2025/04/28
Authors	: Franjo Pehar/UNIZD
Contributors	:
Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	: 10.5281/zenodo.15340523

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Document Log

Version	Date	Description	Name/Partner
v0.1	2025-02-25	Full draft for internal WP6 review	Franjo Pehar/UNIZD
v0.2	2025-03-20	Reviews	Mate Juric/UNIZD, Nikolina Peša Pavlović/UNIZD
v1.0	2025-04-28	Final version	Franjo Pehar/UNIZD

Abstract

This milestone report (MS10) presents the validation of the User-Centred Quality Framework (UCQ-FRAME) within the OPERAS-PLUS project. The framework has been applied to the GoTriple discovery platform, a core service within the OPERAS infrastructure. Developed in accordance with ISO 9241 standards and human-centred design principles, UCQ-FRAME was evaluated using a triangulated approach combining heuristic evaluation (HE), moderated usability testing (MUT) and unmoderated remote usability testing (URUT).

The evaluation process highlighted key strengths of the GoTriple platform, including its multilingual navigation, clear visual design and strong support for exploratory research. It also identified areas for improvement, such as the quality of metadata, the usability of filters and the clarity of domain-specific terminology.

A key contribution of this work lies in the methodological triangulation itself. By integrating expert review, user behaviour and perception-based insights, the approach revealed issues and opportunities that would likely have been missed using a single method. This highlights the value of combining methods in complex, multilingual and interdisciplinary contexts.

Importantly, the findings were structured to support actionable change. They enabled service teams to prioritise improvements based on both user needs and technical feasibility. While UCQ-FRAME was not formally revised, the evaluation informed targeted refinements to the heuristic criteria and prioritisation logic specifically tailored to the needs of the OPERAS services.

These findings are now being incorporated into the OPERAS Guide to Human-Centred Design - a living, evolving resource that translates the principles of the framework into practical guidance. As OPERAS services continue to grow and diversify, the Guide will adapt accordingly, providing teams with up-to-date practices, templates and examples based on human-centred UX and usability design.

Looking ahead, future UX work will explore areas such as real-time behavioural analysis through initiatives such as the LUMEN project, which aims to extend GoTriple into new scientific domains.

Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. UCQ-FRAME: From Methodology to Practice	5
3. The validation of the framework: An evaluation of the usability of GoTriple	8
4. Structured insights for actionable change	9
5. Strengthening the framework through real-world use	11
6. What comes next: Bringing UX principles to life through the OPERAS Guide to Human-Centred Design	12
7. Conclusions	13

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

1. Introduction

This milestone report (MS10) marks an important step forward in the OPERAS-PLUS project's efforts to embed user-centred methods in the development and improvement of services across the OPERAS research infrastructure. It documents how we have applied and validated the [User-Centred Quality Framework \(UCO-FRAME\)](#) - introduced in Deliverable D6.1 - through a practical evaluation of the GoTriple discovery platform. What follows is not only a record of our findings, but also a reflection on what we have learned and how these findings can support future service design. All activities were carried out as part of Task 6.3 in Work Package 6: User Engagement and Training.

This work builds directly on the foundations laid in Task 6.2, where the UCQ FRAME was first defined. It also supports the wider OPERAS goal of designing sustainable, inclusive and user-centred services for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). Today's digital research environment demands more than just access to content - researchers also need platforms that are easy to use, multilingual and interoperable with their existing workflows. That's where user-centric quality becomes essential. It's a natural complement to the FAIR Principles of Open Science, extending their reach beyond technical standards into the realm of practical usability and accessibility.

As OPERAS moves towards becoming a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), the importance of user experience evaluation and iteration cannot be overstated. MS10 contributes to this effort by demonstrating the practical application of UCO-FRAME and laying the groundwork for future development - in particular the creation of the OPERAS Guide to Human-Centred Design. This guide will serve as a practical, evolving resource for teams working to improve services, even in the absence of dedicated UX experts.

The evaluation process used a combination of methods - heuristic evaluation (HE), moderated usability testing (MUT) and unmoderated remote usability testing (URUT) - to provide a rounded view of the user experience. This triangulated approach helped to uncover both strengths and usability challenges, including several issues that would likely have gone unnoticed using a single method alone. This reinforces OPERAS' commitment to designing with users, not just for them, and to fostering a collaborative, evidence-based UX culture.

This report provides an overview of the UCO-FRAME, shares key findings from its application to GoTriple, and shows how these findings have been translated into concrete service improvement proposals. It also outlines how this work will feed into the OPERAS Human-centred Design Guide, which will help to put human-centred design into practice across all OPERAS services. Looking ahead, initiatives such as the LUMEN project - which will extend GoTriple to four additional scientific domains - will open new opportunities to explore complex UX topics such as behavioural analysis and real-time user interaction.

2. UCQ-FRAME: From Methodology to Practice

The User-Centred Quality Framework (UCQ-FRAME), first introduced in [Deliverable D6.1](#), provides a structured yet flexible way to apply human-centred design principles throughout the lifecycle of OPERAS services. It is built on the foundation of [ISO 9241-210](#) and informed by both [ResearchOps](#) and service design practices. At its core, the framework ensures that services are developed and improved based on real user needs, expectations and constraints - rather than assumptions.

The framework has been developed through a combination of top-down and bottom-up approaches. Top-down, it draws on international standards, UX literature and established best practice. From the bottom up, it reflects real-world evidence from OPERAS projects, including service documentation, user feedback and previous project results. This combination has resulted in a framework that is both theoretically sound and practically relevant, particularly in the context of social sciences and humanities (SSH) services.

What's in UCQ-FRAME?

The framework is divided into two main components:

- Part A introduces the core principles and essential processes for designing user-centred services.
- Part B provides a practical toolkit of UX methods and examples.

UCQ-FRAME is designed to align with standard UX process stages and supports both agile and linear development models. This makes it adaptable to different types of teams and workflows within the OPERAS infrastructure.

A cycle built around users

At the heart of UCQ-FRAME is a user-centred design cycle tailored for research infrastructures. This cycle supports key stages such as understanding user needs, co-design, prototyping, testing and incorporating feedback. It encourages continuous iteration and fits well with both traditional UCD models and more contemporary DevOps-style workflows.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Figure 1: ISO 9241-210 user-centred design cycle adapted for OPERAS.

A flexible toolkit for every team

Part B of the framework provides a practical method bank that maps specific UX activities to each stage of the design and development process. Among the methods included are, for example:

- Usability testing
- Heuristic evaluation
- Co-design workshops
- Remote feedback tools
- User journey mapping

Each method is accompanied by clear guidance, editable templates and practical examples, making them accessible to teams regardless of previous UX experience or resources. An overview of how these methods are structured within the framework is shown in Figure 2.

Table 6: The methods matrix aligns different methods with the UCD process

Method	Planning	User research	Design solutions	Evaluating the design	Launching & monitoring
Affinity diagramming		●	●	●	●
Card sorting		●	●		
Cognitive walkthrough		●	●		
Competitive analysis	●				●
Content analysis		●	●	●	
Content inventory and audit	●				●
Contextual inquiry		●			
Critical Incident Technique	●	●			●
Cultural probes		●			
Diary Studies		●			
Empathy Maps		●			
Evaluative Research				●	
Eye Tracking				●	●
Focus Groups	●				●
Gap Analysis	●	●			
Heuristic Evaluation			●	●	

Figure 2. Extract from the UX methods available in Part B of UCQ-FRAME

Teams are encouraged to select methods based on three key factors

- The maturity of their project
- The type of insight they need (e.g. behavioural, attitudinal, structural)
- The resources available

More than a method - a mindset

What makes UCQ-FRAME particularly valuable is that it promotes a shared culture of usability, participation and critical reflection. These principles are very much in line with the OPERAS values of openness, inclusivity and sustainability. Through its structured tools and visual models, the framework encourages teams to pause, assess their current practices, identify gaps, and take confident steps towards a more human-centred approach to service design.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

3. **The validation of the framework: An evaluation of the usability of GoTriple**

In order to understand how UCQ-FRAME performs in real-world conditions, we tested it on GoTriple, a multilingual discovery platform designed for interdisciplinary research in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). GoTriple was chosen because of its complexity and broad user base, which includes researchers from different academic backgrounds, language groups and levels of digital literacy. This made it an ideal case for validating the framework and generating meaningful UX insights.

In order to gain a well-rounded view of the user experience, we used a triangulated evaluation approach, combining three complementary UX methods:

- Heuristic Evaluation (HE): UX experts independently evaluated the platform against established usability principles to identify interface issues.
- Moderated Usability Testing (MUT): Real users performed common tasks while being observed in a controlled environment. This helped us understand how usability issues play out in practice, including where users hesitate, get confused or abandon tasks.
- Unmoderated Remote Usability Testing (URUT): A larger group of users tested the platform remotely. Their feedback, including quantitative ratings using tools such as the System Usability Scale (SUS) and the User Experience Questionnaire - Short (UEQ-S), provided insights into overall satisfaction and usage patterns.

This triangulated approach proved essential. It allowed us to identify issues that we might have missed if we'd only used one type of evaluation. For example:

- HE revealed structural design issues - such as inconsistent labels and unclear menu hierarchies - that could undermine long-term usability.
- MUT showed how these issues disrupted task performance in real time, particularly with search filters, citation export and navigation between sections.
- URUT confirmed that many of these challenges were not isolated - they were widespread and impactful.

Together, these methods provided a deeper, more reliable picture of the user experience.

Key findings: Strengths and challenges

The evaluation revealed both positive aspects and clear usability challenges. Strengths frequently cited by users included

- A clean, minimalist interface
- Strong multilingual support
- Rich metadata and support for exploratory searching
- Use of controlled vocabularies and faceted browsing tailored to SSH needs

At the same time, several recurring problems stood out:

- Filters lacked clear feedback, making it hard to tell when or how they were being applied.
- Labels such as "Membership" or "Data Services" caused confusion due to vague or unfamiliar terminology.
- Citation export features were unclear and didn't meet users' expectations for standardised formats.
- Language switching caused confusion, with some users expecting it to filter content (as on other multilingual platforms).

From problems to action

We took a structured approach to translating the findings into practical recommendations. Using a severity-impact-effort model, we assigned priority ratings to each issue. This helped the teams quickly understand which issues needed to be addressed first, and supported planning for both short-term improvements and ongoing development work.

Importantly, we didn't analyse these as just UI bugs. Each problem was seen as a touchpoint within broader user journeys - such as onboarding, search and citation. This perspective helped teams see how even small usability challenges can have a negative effect on trust, efficiency, and overall satisfaction.

What this means for UCQ-FRAME

This case demonstrated that UCQ-FRAME supports the translation of UX research into concrete service improvements. The triangulated approach helped deliver both quick wins and deeper insights to guide long-term development. The GoTriple evaluation highlights the importance of using contextual, multi-method UX research to design an infrastructure that truly meets user needs within the OPERAS ecosystem.

4. Structured insights for actionable change

One of the key goals of the UCQ-FRAME evaluation at GoTriple wasn't just to collect usability data - it was to ensure that the insights we uncovered could lead to meaningful improvements. To achieve this, we didn't just document the findings, we structured them in a way that made it easy for teams to reflect, prioritise and take action. The structure was inspired by service design principles and helped bridge the gap between UX research and day-to-day development work.

Each problem identified - whether through heuristic evaluation, moderated testing or remote usability testing - was assessed on three things

- How serious the issue was
- How much it affected key user journeys

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

- How technically feasible it would be to fix

This approach helped teams distinguish between critical roadblocks (such as confusing labels like "Membership") and more minor improvements (such as adding feedback after login or clarifying how language switching works). In short, we made it easier for teams to act on real evidence and plan improvements efficiently.

Turning confusion into opportunity

The evaluation also revealed a mix of strengths and pain points - and in many cases, user confusion became a springboard for better design. For example, language switching: users appreciated the multilingual interface, but many assumed that changing the interface language would also filter the content. It didn't - and while that's not a bug, it created a mismatch between expectation and reality. Instead of changing the functionality, we recommended adding a simple tooltip or visual cue. This is a good example of how even small design tweaks can resolve misunderstandings and improve the overall experience.

Metadata, citations and mixed signals

The same type of analysis was applied to metadata and citation workflows. Users welcomed the use of TRIPLE vocabulary tags, saying the structured presentation helped them explore topics effectively. But they were frustrated when key metadata fields (such as DOIs or affiliations) or standard citation formats (such as APA or MLA) were missing. These comments helped us see where the current experience was strong, and where a few targeted tweaks could make a big difference to usability.

Seeing patterns, not just problems

Throughout the process, we grouped the issues within the context of broader service journeys - such as search, navigation, citation or onboarding - rather than treating them as isolated interface bugs. This helped teams understand how small friction points can add up over time and impact bigger things like user trust, perceived reliability or the number of support requests.

To take this further, we also organised the findings around experience themes - recurring patterns that pointed to deeper UX priorities. These included

- Trust and transparency, which emerged in areas such as login, metadata completeness and citation accuracy
- Orientation and navigation, which relied heavily on clear labelling and consistent structure
- Cross-language discoverability, which was influenced by how language switching, filters and interface text behaved across different languages.

These issues helped spark deeper conversations within the team - not just about fixing individual problems, but about clarifying user goals, shaping platform strategy, and aligning around a long-term UX vision.

Building capacity through clarity

By structuring the findings in a clear and accessible way, we made it possible for teams with different levels of UX experience to use them confidently. That's a key aim of UCQ-FRAME: to promote user-centred quality as a shared responsibility, not something reserved for UX specialists.

This approach also sets the stage for what comes next. The same process of capturing, prioritising and applying user feedback will form the basis of the *OPERAS Guide to Human-Centred Design*. As teams use it, they'll be able to build their own UX maturity, one insight - and one improvement - at a time.

5. Strengthening the framework through real-world use

The implementation of the UCQ framework on the GoTriple platform showed that its core components work - and matter - in practice. The framework proved to be both adaptable and genuinely helpful, supporting teams to apply user-centred design in a complex, real-world setting. This practical experience also provided space to reflect on how the framework could be further refined to better support teams working within the unique challenges of research infrastructures.

Making prioritisation more practical

One of the key lessons learned was the need for a stronger prioritisation model. While using severity ratings to flag usability issues was helpful, it didn't go far enough. To improve this, we introduced a model that combined severity, impact on user journeys and estimated effort to resolve the issue.

This gave teams a clearer way to differentiate:

- Quick, high-impact fixes
- Strategic, long-term improvements
- Issues that required further investigation

This alignment made insights more actionable and helped align UX work with development priorities and capacity.

Recognising the limitations of general heuristics

Another key insight came from the limitations of traditional usability heuristics in specialised environments such as SSH. While Nielsen's ten usability principles provided a strong foundation, they didn't always fit the challenges we faced - such as multilingual search, metadata inconsistencies, or navigation across disciplinary silos.

This highlighted the need to adapt heuristic criteria to reflect the realities of scholarly platforms, where language diversity, metadata complexity and cross-disciplinary research are the norm. It's not that general heuristics failed - but they didn't cover everything that was important in this context.

From framework to strategy

What's emerging here is a broader shift: UCQ-FRAME is no longer just a checklist or a

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

set of tools. It's becoming a strategic resource that helps teams embed user-centred thinking into the way they plan, build and collaborate.

Its flexibility has made it particularly useful for interdisciplinary teams managing evolving platforms under real-world constraints. More than that, its use is helping to build a shared UX culture within OPERAS - one based on learning, reflection and evidence-based decision making.

What comes next

These lessons are now informing the next step: the development of the OPERAS Guide to Human-Centred Design. This guide will bring the principles of UCQ-FRAME to life through practical tools, methods and examples that teams can use - whether they're building something new or improving an existing service.

By making UX methods more accessible and easier to apply, the guide will help make user-centred quality a natural part of everyday work - not a special task reserved for UX specialists. In this way, every OPERAS team can participate in creating services that truly meet the needs of the communities they serve.

6. What comes next: Bringing UX principles to life through the OPERAS Guide to Human-Centred Design

The successful application of UCQ-FRAME throughout OPERAS has built a strong foundation - not just in theory, but in daily practice. This now paves the way for the next step: the creation of the OPERAS Guide to Human-Centred Design.

This guide is a practical, evolving resource to help teams across the OPERAS infrastructure design and improve services in a user-centred way. It takes the core principles of UCQ-FRAME and translates them into accessible tools, methods and guidance that teams can apply directly to their work - whether they are experienced in UX or just starting out.

A flexible resource for diverse teams

The guide is:

- Modular and adaptable, supporting both the development of new services and the improvement of existing platforms
- Inclusive and accessible, especially for teams without formal UX roles
- Adaptable to different roles, including designers, developers, product owners and coordinators

Key components include

- Templates for user research, usability testing and prioritisation
- Tools to help teams select appropriate UX methodologies based on project goals, available skills and time constraints

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

- Decision support and journey mapping guides tailored to different service contexts
- Case studies from GoTriple and other OPERAS services to illustrate real-world applications and best practices

Support for UX capability and shared practice

Beyond providing tools, the guide will help build UX capacity across the OPERAS community. By making UX practices accessible and replicable, it promotes a shared understanding of user-centred quality - one that can be embedded in everyday decisions, rather than reserved for experts.

Importantly, this is not a static deliverable. The OPERAS Guide to Human-centred Design will be a living resource, regularly updated as new challenges emerge and services evolve. It will grow with OPERAS, incorporating new methods, tools and examples to remain relevant and useful.

Preparing for future challenges

Looking ahead, several areas of focus are already on the horizon:

- Real-time behaviour tracking
- Adaptive user interfaces
- Smarter cross-domain search experiences
- Human–AI collaboration in user research, ideation, and design (e.g. through LLMs)

These issues will be explored through projects such as LUMEN and GRAPHIA, which will provide a valuable test bed for the further development and refinement of the Guide.

From framework to practice

The *OPERAS Guide to Human-Centred Design* is a natural next step in the evolution of UCQ-FRAME - turning a robust framework into a practical tool for everyday work. It will support teams in building services that are not only functional, but also inclusive, intuitive and responsive to the real needs of the research communities they serve.

7. Conclusions

This milestone report represents a significant step forward for the OPERAS-PLUS project. It shows clear progress in embedding user-centred quality as a key part of how services are designed, evaluated and improved across the OPERAS research infrastructure.

Through the real-world application of UCQ-FRAME on GoTriple - a complex, multilingual platform - we have demonstrated that structured UX methods can thrive in diverse, interdisciplinary environments. In addition, the process generated actionable insights that influenced service design, iteration cycles and long-term planning.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

The evaluation helped to clarify what was working well on GoTriple and where improvements were needed. A key achievement was translating the findings into clear, prioritised recommendations that the teams could act on immediately. The use of multiple methods - heuristic evaluation, moderated testing and unmoderated remote testing - confirmed the value of triangulation and provided a richer and more reliable view of the user experience.

This work seeks to encourage an important shift in thinking. UX is no longer seen as a single testing phase - it's recognised as a continuous, collaborative effort to improve the usability, accessibility and inclusivity of OPERAS services.

The lessons learned from this work (Task 6.3) are now being incorporated into the OPERAS Guide to Human-Centred Design - a practical, flexible resource that translates the UCQ framework into tools, methods and guidance for everyday use. This guide is designed to support all teams, whether they're creating new services or improving existing ones, and regardless of their previous experience with UX.

Looking ahead, OPERAS will continue to grow, and with that growth comes new opportunities to test, refine and extend UX practices. The impact of UCQ-FRAME - and the user-centred thinking it promotes - is expected to extend well beyond this project, helping to shape services that are more usable, inclusive and trusted across the OPERAS infrastructure.

Finally, this report reinforces a central idea: user involvement is not a one-off activity - it's an ongoing commitment. By working with shared tools, embedded practices and collaborative approaches, OPERAS can ensure that its services evolve in line with the real needs and expectations of the research communities they are designed to support.

